

Tracing the infrastructural unfolding of (edtech) events through hybrid team ethnography

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ABSTRACT

This article contributes to expanding discussions on the rising hybridity of (edtech) events and, in conjunction to that, of ethnographic (edtech) event research. With hybridity, we point to the increasing postdigital condition of contemporary society. Even though such hybridity, and its methodological consequences for ethnographic research, are increasingly discussed, few attention has so far been put on how this hybridity manifests in, and is mediated through, orchestrations of data infrastructures. This article presents hybrid team ethnography as a way to study, and at the same time be intricately interwoven with, such infrastructure-mediated hybridity. Concretely, we report on an ethnography in which we studied an event in the edtech startup sector. Our findings showcase how researchers co-construct and are shaped by events, not just through dynamic interplays between physical presence-absence, but equally through data infrastructures and research(er) presentation. Moreover, they simultaneously showcase how edtech events unfold infrastructurally over space and time.

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Introduction

This article provides an in-depth discussion of *hybrid team ethnography* as a methodological approach to collectively investigate tech events and their infrastructural unfoldings in the educational field. It hereby contributes to the growing field of *tech event studies*; that is, events that seek to promote and diffuse technological developments (Rosental 2023). One example of such events are *edtech fairs*, whose main purpose is the promotion and putting into the spotlight of newly developed edtech products, as well as the successful spreading of products towards end user markets, such as schools and classrooms (e.g., Gulson and Witzenberger 2022; Player-Koro, Bergviken Rensfeldt, and Selwyn 2018; 2022). Importantly, digital technologies, in this regard, not only permeate edtech events as products (i.e., forming the content that the event is about); they equally increasingly serve as the (*data*) *infrastructural backbone* of such events. That is to say, edtech events are increasingly relying on the creation of (dis-)connectivity through large platform architectures (e.g., that host their website), social media (e.g., in order to announce, and

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distribute information about, the event), and complementing dedicated apps (e.g., containing the event's calendar and participant list).

In order to account for the considerable complexities and highly dynamic nature of events, methodologically, studies within the tech event field have most commonly made use of ethnographic approaches (e.g., Zukin and Papadantonakis 2017). This resonates with more general literature on event studies that has described events as multi-actor assemblages that are – within their temporal boundedness (Koch 2023) – continuously unfolding and changing in multiple ways (Nail 2017). Put differently, events are characterized by many (often surprising) things happening at once, of which it is impossible to predict precise outcomes in advance, but which rather need to be traced ethnographically and carefully in their gradual unfolding (Wagner-Pacifici 2019; Nail 2017). Drawing on the broad ethnographic tradition of ‘being there’ through participatory observation and on the specific tradition of multi-sited ethnography, which defines as its objective the study of phenomena ‘that cannot be accounted for by focusing on a single site’ (Falzon 2016, 1), event ethnography considers events as ‘important sites not *despite* the fact that they are temporary, but *because* they are temporary’ (Koch 2023, 2). At the same time, through their specific context of (and capacity towards) highly condensed meaning-making, events carry a significant power to (re)configure specific (e.g., professional) fields (e.g., Campbell et al. 2014; Jaimangal-Jones 2014; Van Dooremalen 2017; Schulte-Römer and Gesing 2023). In other words, in their unfolding, events *form and create specific sorts of visibilities and realities* (Kapferer 2010). They do so by orchestrating formerly unrelated (or differently related) actors or elements in a specific way, complemented by techniques of persuasion, dramaturgy, ceremony, and spectacle (Cook and Ward 2012; Lampel and Meyer 2008; McCann and Ward 2012). As we argue in this article, even though edtech events are to a growing extent subject of critical ethnographic research (often adopting a network perspective – see e.g., Player-Koro, Jobér, and Bergviken Rensfeldt 2022; Ball 2016; Junemann, Ball, and Santori 2018; Avelar et al. 2018; and Peck and Theodore 2012 for an example from the broader social sciences), and even though the governance capacities of data infrastructures have been highlighted recently (Williamson 2022), there is still a significant lack of attention devoted to the data infrastructural backbone of events. This data infrastructural backbone not only crucially co-shapes how events evolve and which realities are being created there, but equally significantly affects – as much as it is affected by – the analogue-digital practices of ethnographic investigation themselves. In other words, we still lack a profound understanding of how the *data infrastructuring* – the relations and practices that are formed and evolve when data infrastructures come into being, and that similarly enact these very infrastructures – of edtech events on the one hand, and the data infrastructuring of ethnographic research on the other hand, relate to, and impact, one another.

In this paper, we seek to address that gap by analytically reflecting on an edtech event studied through what we call a *hybrid team ethnography*. The study brought together eight scholars from (back then) two different universities and countries, who over a period of one year (preparation of the study, ethnographic fieldwork, and data analysis included) conducted an ethnographic study in order to better understand the structures and operationalities of the rapidly emerging European edtech startup sector (see for results of that study Decuyper et al. 2024). Across all stages of the study, the dynamic interlinkage between analogue practices and digital (dis-)connectivity – i.e., the simultaneous data infrastructuring of both the event and the ethnography – formed a key interest of the research team. While the team could indeed build on a growing amount of literature around ‘digital methods’ in general (e.g., Pink et al. 2015; Venturini et al. 2018), and ‘hybrid ethnography’ in particular (e.g., Przybylski 2020; Liu 2022; James and Busher 2013), we found that hardly any of that literature has specifically addressed the particularities of ethnographic hybridity and data infrastructuring for *larger research team constellations*. This seems all the more relevant since educational research is increasingly relying on such collaborative research approaches that not only exceed local boundaries (e.g., transnational research teams), but that also more and more rely – oftentimes unconsciously – on the affordances of digital-collaborative technologies (e.g., data

sharing platforms, messaging platforms, online collaborative document editors) in doing so. Hence, with this paper, we seek to offer a more systematic and analytical lens through which such data infrastructuring can be methodologically approached, as well as being critically reflected on, as *integral part of hybrid team research*.

Hybrid ethnography: A methodological response to the postdigital condition of contemporary society

Little surprisingly, the critical engagement with hybrid ethnography stems from the growing omnipresence of digital technologies in our lives, which has made it increasingly difficult to make distinctions between the online and the offline; the digital and the analogue; etc. In the social sciences, this growing interwovenness has *inter alia* been conceptualized as ‘postdigital condition’ (Jandric et al. 2018; Arantes and Buchanan 2023), as ‘culture of digitality’ (Stalder 2021) or as ‘hybrid ecology’ (Schulte-Römer and Gesing 2023), and it has been complemented by growing debates around necessary consequential transformations of methodological and scholarly practices.

In the field of ethnography, the gradual emergence of scholarship on ‘hybrid ethnography’ is a clear manifestation of those debates. Importantly, while the term ‘hybrid’ has been used to capture various forms of mixed or blurred forms of ethnography (see, for instance, Seim [2021] who uses hybridity to describe a mix between participant observation and observant participation), in this article, we only focus on research that uses the term with regards to the intensifying postdigital nature of society, and its implications for ethnography. As Liu (2022:, 2) states: ‘little research has addressed how ethnographers adapt tools for this new reality and how they consider the implications of retooled processes’. In other words, the necessity of the concept of hybrid ethnography is not only situated in the need to discuss the pragmatic pros and cons of (not) deploying different analogue and digital tools, for instance with regards to the enhancing of field access, or the facilitating of data collection and analysis (Ens, Stein, and Jensen 2023; Collins et al. 2017; Kaufmann and Peil 2020; Kleinlein 2023). Over and beyond that, the concept points to the actual intricacies of conducting such new forms of ethnographic research. That is to say, the research field itself is being reconceptualized through the orchestration of such hybridity, including *what* the research field is, *where* it can be found, or *when* it is actually taking place (Liu 2022, 2; Alcadipani and Cunliffe 2024; Przybylski 2020; Tummons 2020).

Amongst the scarce, yet growing body of literature on hybrid ethnography, Schulte-Römer and Gesing (2023, 1620) have specifically applied the approach to the investigation of events in order to identify ‘[...] key challenges related to the spatio-temporal ephemerality, socio-material infrastructures and interactive unboundedness of events’. First of all, the *spatiotemporal ephemerality* of events points to the fact that events, in general, only last for a very short time: ‘events simply cease to exist after they have taken place and you cannot revisit what you may have missed’ (p.1624). For hybrid ethnography, this implies the need to continuously reflect on the allocation of resources – be they time, money, and/or scholarly attention – since the allocation of these resources will determine the data researchers gather and hence, ultimately, the (shape and sort of) event that is being reported of. Especially for that reason, our study differs from traditional ethnographic research designs as they are most typically being showcased in the literature; that is, as research that is commonly investigated by one single person doing the fieldwork (even though more collaborative approaches exist both in the general field of ethnography [e.g., Lassiter 2005] and in the more specific field of event ethnography [e.g., Campbell et al. 2014]). In contrast, our ethnography was from the start designed to be conducted by a team of eight scholars from (back then) two different universities and countries (two PIs and six doctoral students). This had foremost strategic reasons that aimed to engage with this ephemerality, since the event was so big that it was uncoverable by a single ethnographer doing the fieldwork alone (Campbell et al. 2014, 9). At the same time, the team constellation equally had significant implications for the ‘infrastructured world-making’ within the hybrid ethnography for two reasons. On the one hand, each individual researcher was

engaging with and through the infrastructural unfolding of the event/research, as such co-constructing different versions of the event through online-offline data collection or communication. On the other hand, there equally was a collective dimension involved within each step of the hybrid ethnography, namely when trying to build, and act as, a *team* – or, as Campbell et al. (2014) phrase it, when trying to develop ‘dispersed consciousness’. Acting as a *team*, at the same time, allowed us to anchor traditional ideas of ethnography, such as the deliberate reflection on one’s own research and on the role and impact of the researcher in the practices one is investigating, at a very early state in the process, namely already in the gathering of the data.

Second, events are always taking place in a certain dedicated *infrastructure*. Indeed, the building of, and acting as, a team was strongly facilitated, mediated by, and enacted through, data infrastructures. As mentioned above, these infrastructures are not to be understood as ‘just being there’, but are always in the process of being performed: they are *infrastructuring*. Infrastructuring comprises ‘heterogeneous process[es] of organizing, forming audiences and forging attachments, dependencies, and commitments during events. It highlights that access and observability are closely intertwined with the specific socio-materiality of event settings – including ticket control barriers, seating orders around meeting tables, exhibition designs, or ICT functionalities in a virtual conference space’ (Schulte-Römer and Gesing 2023, 1628). Moreover, given the author team’s own central positioning in *data infrastructure research* (e.g., Hartong and Förschler 2019; Decuyper 2021), we chose to approach this hybridity explicitly through this specific lens, and this to better capture in detail what the literature frames as *hybrid relationality*. With this is meant that, in each moment, both digital and analogue practices are being transferred into data infrastructuring logics; that is, they become intertwined with, and highly dependent on, proxy generation, algorithmic processing, data flowability, and data practices to secure this relational flux and flow (Stalder 2021; see also Lewis and Hartong 2022). Such datafied (re-)making of relations, then, creates specific (in-)visibilities, spacetimes, or realities that researchers need to operate in, as well as at the same time make (one of the) subject(s) of analysis (Piattoeva and Saari 2022). This more specific focus can contribute to an arguably more nuanced understanding of how exactly the data infrastructural backbone of both events and ethnographic research operate in conjunction.

Third, the *unboundedness* of events has to do with the fact that many exchanges between participants take place informally, sometimes somewhat messy and spontaneously, and often without even precisely knowing who one is exactly interacting with. As Schulte-Römer and Gesing (2023) suggest, this has important repercussions for researchers, in the sense that they continuously need to reflect on how exactly to position themselves *as* researchers, and on the ways in which (not) to disclose oneself as actually being a researcher (given that ethnographers always *necessarily* form and co-shape the field they are researching to some extent).

Introducing the case: the hybridity of an edtech event

The edtech event we investigated was especially targeting the European *edtech startup sector*, which is a sector populated by many young corporations that are often still in the process of crafting their first original products and/or business models (Decuyper et al. 2024). At the event, many activities that were addressing this specific characteristic of the field were taking place simultaneously (e.g., training startups in attracting investors; offering success stories from startups that eventually ‘made it’ in the educational field; etc.). The event took place over a duration of three days in a medium-sized western European city, mainly addressing founders who were in the development process of an educational solution or had already launched their product, as well as investors and organizations supporting edtech startups. Including various formats (e.g., workshop pavilions, master classes, exhibitions), more than 1,000 participants and 150 speakers presented their products, got into contact with each other, and learned more about building/scaling up edtech startups. The actual event was taking place on-site, and apart from the evening program, all activities were located in the same venue. The program was spread out over several stages, so that during each program

Figure 1. Floor plan of the event.

slot, approximately 5 sessions took place simultaneously. Next to these sessions, there was a rotating exhibition, in which the exhibitors changed twice a day. For 1:1 meetings and further networking opportunities, the event venue offered a couple of bars, a food court, and a lounge that was only accessible for the speakers on the event. There was equally a backstage, where the organizers had their headquarters for the duration of the event (Figure 1).

Complementing these on-site activities, the event was ‘held together’ by an extensive data infrastructural backbone of platforms and social media; infrastructures that were creating their own spacetimes of interaction and collaboration. For instance, all participants were informed about latest developments via frequent newsletters (mostly closely connected to updates of the event website), and they were strongly encouraged to make use of the event’s dedicated app. The app provided a regularly updated program, sent popup notifications, and gave participants the opportunity to set up an own profile to virtually communicate with others or to arrange meetings in advance. All this was further complemented by a complex arrangement of screens, wi-fi networks, photographing/photo displaying, and video recordings.

In what follows, and along the three dimensions outlined in the framework above, we present our analysis of how the hybrid and infrastructured character of the event co-unfolded with our hybrid and infrastructured character of the team ethnography. The findings illuminate the manifoldness of this co-unfolding, and the powerful – yet at the same time equally highly contingent – role of data infrastructures herein.

Navigating between infrastructures

Creating and sustaining collectivity through/despite infrastructures

From the moment of initiating the study, we as researchers were confronted with the challenge of spatiotemporal coordination and (non)connectedness, which, however, manifested differently *before* (being spread out over four different European cities and being differently integrated into university schedules), *during* (being in the same venue for all three days, even though, for most times, being dispersed across different parts or places of the event) and *after* (with the first author of this article having moved countries and universities during the data analysis phase) the event. Already before the event, we devoted substantial effort to the question how we could create a hybrid

infrastructure that could serve as the backbone of our study design, data collection and analysis. For instance, it was crucial that, by means of this infrastructure, the team could communicate and act collectively despite this spatiotemporal dispersion. The same applied to the event organizers, with whom we did not have direct contact in the first phases of our preparations, but who we ‘saw’ through their intensive engagement with the setup of mailing lists, newsletters, and the event homepage, all of them seeking to address a community of future event participants (see also Förschler and Decuyper 2024). In other words, even though the physical taking place of the event could be characterized as being ephemeral, the (researching of the) event needed to be coordinated and connected in many ways, both during and after its actual manifestation.

On the researchers’ side, we decided to rely on an orchestration of three different *digital team spaces*. Each of those space came with own potentials and affordances, as well as with specific limitations and drawbacks. The first one was *MS Teams*, a platform that allowed collaboration in the form of video conferencing as well as collective writing or editing of documents. The second one was *TeamDrive*, a platform that allowed for secure cloud storage of research data. The third one was *Signal*, a messenger app that allowed us to exchange ideas and data in real-time, and that is more data secure than other more conventional alternatives (see also below). In that respect, the adherence to data security requirements of different universities in different countries significantly influenced the choices we made. At the same time, we tried to create a data infrastructure where the entire team could continuously engage in processes of dialogic engagement (Ravitch and Carl 2021). In addition, the platformed data infrastructure facilitated keeping everyone up to date with regards to the ethnographic research design and effectuation, including the sharing of data that were collected and analyzed in preparation of (and during) the event. For instance, one member of the research team conducted an online intake interview with the event organizer, and the anonymized interview transcript was shared, so that every team member could gain insights into the results.

As noted above, during the preparatory stage, our research data infrastructure temporally unfolded and evolved with the gradual setup of the event’s data infrastructure. This means that, despite the aforementioned interview, all insights into the field, including our preparation of the ethnography visit itself, were generated from this infrastructure – newsletters, e-mails, the event’s website and program, etc.. Put differently, we got to see a picture of connected collectivity, in the sense that we could (only) see with and through what the event organizers offered us and the other participants before the event – again challenging the strictly bounded ephemeral nature of such events. Naturally, this picture changed when we went into direct (online or on site) interaction with people attending the event.

During the event, our spatial orchestration of meeting spaces shifted substantially, since we were provided a backstage room in which we could always come physically together (see Figure 1). Particularly at the beginning and end of each day, we gathered in this backstage room to discuss observations, share experiences, and eventually adjust and cohere the research for the next day. We perceived this on-site space as significantly less pre-structured and ‘organized’ than our online meeting spaces. This was particularly true for the data collection and exchange via the Signal group (see next section), which all researchers perceived as not only enhancing possibilities of exchange, but simultaneously as limiting the quality and depth of shared impressions and collective meaning generation. In other words, the physical meeting spaces were found of key importance to individually and collectively ‘digest’ the impressions of the event, and to ‘balance out’ the strongly pre-structured data practices set up before the event took the start (see also Liu 2022).

Whilst observing the event, we noticed that equally the event organizers deliberately attempted to create collective spirit (e.g., by placing a rodeo unicorn in the main hall, distributing LEGO sets across the tables, having the opportunity to arrange meetings with each other via the app, etc.). Interestingly, despite this interaction, many participants still – and particularly after the first day – spent a significant amount of time (individually) on their computers or smartphones, oftentimes leading to situations where many people sat in one room while working in an isolated manner (and

not listening to what was happening on stage). This attests to the fact that, even though the event infrastructure was explicitly set up in such a way as to facilitate exchange and interaction, this infrastructure often came into contact with *other* infrastructures and infrastructural dynamics, who were sometimes unplanned or even juxtaposed to the envisaged finalities of the event infrastructure itself. This shows that event infrastructures are never positioned in a vacuum, but always meet and encounter other (e.g., personal, institutional, etc.) infrastructural dynamics.

In the aftermath of the event, the organizers immediately initiated their online promotion for the next year's follow-up event, and again strongly relied on platforms and digital material to sustain the collective spirit of the event. Equally the research team returned to the foremost digital assemblage of meeting spaces for data analysis and processing. At the same time, these research infrastructure spaces were now 'filled' with many (structured) data. It is to these practices of infrastructuring research data that we turn next.

Data (not) becoming part of digital data infrastructures

As with any other kind of ethnographic research, the collection, processing and (iterative) analysis of research data formed the center of our study. Consequently, it was particularly this part where the implications of installing a particular form of hybrid infrastructure became clearly visible.

To begin with, we intensively discussed how we could design a methodological approach of data collection that would be flexible enough to match the highly dynamic nature of the event. Before and after the event, we could quite easily collect, store, and analyze the digital newsletters sent by the organizers or the webpage content of the event, even though we needed to keep up with continuous updates. Equally the online interview that one of us conducted with the organizers before the event, was transcribed and uploaded on our digital team spaces. In contrast, during the three days of the event, the amount and dynamism of data collection (both on site – e.g., on stage – and online – e.g., in the app) was much more overwhelming, which mirrored what both many participants as well as the organizers were experiencing ('there is so much going on'). For instance, whilst we as researchers tried to keep an overview of everything that was going on, but equally continuously sought to pick the 'right sessions' to investigate our research questions, we were equally frequently prompted by the app to 'not miss today's highlights' – which is one of the many ways in which the event sought to affectively bring (and hold) together its participants. In order to cover as many activities as possible and at the same time see as much as possible when attending those activities, we always paired two researchers together to attend the same sessions. This allowed us to have enough 'sub-teams' to cover the different parts of the fair, but, more importantly, it equally allowed us to share, and dialogically engage about, the observed sessions with a physical partner.

To respond to these conditions in the best possible manner, we decided for an ongoing 'slaloming' strategy between on- and offline methods (Jensen 2022). At the same time, we explored how tools and data practices might be used (differently than is typically done) in ethnographic research, in ways that particularly addressed this highly vibrant and complex environment (Kleinlein 2023). More particularly, we developed a twofold data collection process that at once included analogue fieldnotes (plus selected interviews, see next section) *and* tools for interactive digital data collection. While the research team agreed on specific observation foci, the analogue paper notebooks turned out to be filled in very distinct, personal ways, in each person's native language, and oftentimes in ways that the other team members could not even read or make sense of. In contrast, the Signal messaging system played the role of a digital notebook and, through its specific affordances, made different practices (im)possible than the analogue notebooks did. For instance, it allowed us to ongoingly take photos of interesting presentation slides, artefacts (e.g., promotion material of edtech companies present), as well as the general set-up of talks and sessions. It equally made possible to record voice memos directly after each session, which could, then, be shared with the other team members instantaneously. Yet, the affordances of Signal equally often made things (initially) impossible, such as the creation of different groups with the same team members –

Figure 2. The instant messaging app as collection device for written, visual, and auditive data (left); The protocol used when recording voice messages, displayed as Signal's group image (right).

something we only managed to do with a technical workaround. Moreover, to not get too overwhelmed with data and to steer the data collection procedure in a dedicated direction, we equally created a structured voice memo protocol in advance (see Figure 2) as well as different chat groups that matched the venue stages (e.g., 'Main stage, Day 1').

The introduction of 'asynchronous narrative audio messages' (Kleinlein 2023), together with photographs and the analogue notebooks, triggered different practices in the research team. To begin with, while we as researchers indeed tried to stick to the outlined protocol as much as possible, there were also frequent 'outlier moments', in which one of us got, for instance, carried away by impressions that we urgently wanted to share. Equally, even though we agreed to limit the duration of the voice memos, this was not always possible. Moreover, the combination of voice messages and photographs for all researchers felt like a unique way to present and, most importantly, to directly share observations, which also meant to relate them to observations others made. Everybody felt inspired by these instant impressions that the Signal group allowed us to immediately share with each other, and as having been 'a little bit in that session, too', even though one could not be physically present. The feeling of having a 'sparring partner' for the observations, as well as the shared protocol to stick to, even evoked some duos to recording their voice messages together (even if that was not the original intention). Put differently, some duos dynamically adjusted the data collection method of voice memos to unite their individual perspectives. Similarly, some of us used the voice memos to critically discuss the notebook content that we had created during our observations, which means that the voice memos, in a way, offered a mode of additional 'instant reflection' on the research process. In contrast, even though the combination of notes, audio memos, and photographs deliberately aimed at providing contextual information, we all felt (and reported to each

other) that a gap between ‘having been there’ and ‘seeing the session through notes, memos, and pictures’ still continued to exist.

In our view, this combined orchestration of on- and offline methods made the process of data collection and analysis possible in forms and intensity that could not have been shown or communicated in the same manner if they would have been solely collected through analogue *or* digital means (Liu 2022). Additionally, this specific combination of on- and offline methods enabled us to properly collect data as a *team* and to bundle observations already during the event instead of sharing individual data afterwards. At the same time, each tool we brought into this orchestration carried specific affordances with it, which heavily co-shaped our data collection process. In particular with regards to the written field notes, all members of the research team felt that those not only possessed a unique and private quality (they were for instance, written in the researcher’s own mother tongue - which was not necessarily English - including references, and often contained linkages to one’s own individual research), but equally that they provided unique, sensitive, and sometimes directly identifiable information about the persons interviewed and/or practices observed. For those reasons, those notes were *not* shared with the entire research team (and are equally not exemplarily included in the present article for purposes of illustration). Moreover, the decision for a specific combination of tools equally sometimes limited our awareness for what was happening in alternative infrastructures, for instance the event app, which we only used to get more information about participants or to check program updates. The organizers, in turn, much more strongly relied on the app to keep the overview and to communicate analogue observations (for instance, if a stage was lacking audience). Hence, what we clearly see here is that while many infrastructural components co-evolved, we in the research team also created deliberate *cuts* from that event infrastructure, in order to focus more strongly on our own endeavor.

Finally, at the last day of the event, we intensively discussed how the collected data would be integrated in order to start more systematic analysis. The hybridity of our data hereby posed a significant challenge since only the integration of data would foster a ‘thick description’ (Geertz 1973) of the event, while the on- and offline data equally required to keep their authenticity. Here, we particularly experienced that the analogue notebooks could not be easily ‘streamlined’ with the otherwise digital infrastructure, without losing important context and nuance (e.g., how things had been written, underlined, drawn). Interestingly, during that process, as a team we somehow felt a subtle pressure to *prioritize the digital data*, because they were already infrastructured in digital manners and, hence, could be shared or analyzed more easily. In contrast, we felt that the analogue notebooks ‘meant’ the most to us, and that we even wanted to keep them individually with ourselves (rather than, for instance, one researcher taking all the notebooks with him/her). In the end, we intentionally decided to only streamline (i.e., integrate into one database) the digitally collected data (voice memos, transcripts, pictures) on TeamDrive, and to keep the field notes in their original analogue form and with individual people. This also meant, however, that during data analysis, all members needed to take continuous care that the field notes were ‘brought in’, since it was, infrastructurally speaking, continuously at risk of being ‘left behind’ from the digital data infrastructure developed (Leone 2020). Moreover, the usage of Teams and TeamDrive for the purposes of data storage and communication (which allowed for theoretically endless storage of data, but which at the same time highly structured the sorts of communication that were possible), in conjunction with the information gathered in the field notes and the asynchronous voice messages, made that the data analysis process was in a constant danger of information overload – a challenge that nearly every ethnography struggles with, but that is greatly enhanced when making use of digital infrastructures. Moreover, the synchronization of data and research findings across platforms and across universities proved to be a constant challenge (despite corporate promises of effortless synchronization). This continuously impacted the process of data analysis (divided into subgroups in order to ascertain manageability), as well as the generation and eventual presentation of coherent analytical themes (see Decuyper et al. 2024, for the elaborated argument).

Researchers (not) becoming part of messy event infrastructures

The highly dynamic nature of the edtech event meant that we frequently needed to spontaneously adapt the research design to ‘unexpected connections, mutations, and research sites’ (McCann and Ward 2012, 43). Even if events are thoroughly planned beforehand, they always unfold in partly unexpected ways, due to the individual practices of participants, surrounding conditions, as well as due to the very activities that the *researchers themselves* perform during the event (Wagner-Pacifici 2019). Taking this insight seriously, we sought to be as prepared as possible before the event took the start. The voice messages and fieldnotes protocols were two of the many ‘strategies of infrastructuring’ that we employed to systematize and plan the sound effectuation of our research, despite the fact that we equally anticipated a certain amount of messiness to manifest (Law 2004). The same applied to the event organizers, who used the aforementioned platforms and artefacts (e.g., the constantly updated event program) in order to pre-structure the event as best as possible. Despite these investments, however, it was clearly visible how both us researchers and the event team needed to adapt to spontaneous messiness – what Lewis (2021) termed ‘methodological ad-hocery’ – that each time manifested differently within, or was triggered by, the infrastructure of the event.

For instance, we spent substantial amounts of time before the event to set up on-site interview appointments with participants. We invited participants through the event newsletter, as such becoming visible to all the participants, and becoming inextricably part of the event itself. Ultimately, we were able to arrange 15 on-site interviews. Yet, as soon as the event started, communication for participants (and for us) became much more dynamic, with instant messages popping up in the app at whatever time, and individual event schedules being ‘formed’ through the app as well. Being confronted with all the app’s notifications, we doubted if our interview appointments might get lost in the constant stream of activities. Moreover, the app’s strong presence made us unsure which communication channel to use to reconfirm the appointments with our respondents. Indeed, multiple times our interview partners did not show up, even though they were active in the event (and, probably, in the app). We did find other participants back by integrating our communication into the app, or by calling them. Yet, some of them asked to reschedule the interview after the event, since it would be easier for them to be ‘reliably present online’. In contrast, we also arranged interviews spontaneously on-site when talking to people, which affected the sample collected previous to the event.

Another example of (the need to navigate) infrastructurally mediated mess, was the rotating exhibition. During the pre-interview with the event organizer, we were informed that this exhibition would form one of the centerpieces of the summit. The exhibition would present various actors and products from the field, and provide participants with opportunities for informal engagement. Given this strong emphasis on the exhibition, as a research team, we arranged the observation schedule in such a way that there always were researchers present there. However, when being present during the event, it turned out that there was hardly anything happening (and thus, hardly anyone present) at the exhibition space. Even though this, in a way, formed a key research finding (showing the relative smaller importance of this exhibition for the participants than, for instance, the master classes or keynote speeches), it equally meant that we needed to redirect the observation schedule accordingly. What this example consequently shows is the ‘organizational messiness’ of events, in the sense that actual interactions have the potential to reshape (intended) infrastructuring.

Lastly, we would like to further discuss the probably most important self-critical question we as researchers ongoingly asked ourselves: in how far did we (need to) become part of the event and its infrastructural backbone, and what did that integration imply for our positioning as researchers (beyond the basic point that, as ethnographers, one always inevitably impacts the event that is being studied)? This question addressed the visibility of our research, but equally the amount of ‘merging’ between our practices and the infrastructural logics of the event. While we already outlined different areas where such ‘merging’ took place and/or where it affected our research (e.g.,

using the event app), we would like to discuss one more example that clearly showcases the extent to which we, as researchers, *became (part of) the event*. From the beginning, our research team intensively discussed whether or not, and how much, we needed to be transparent about our research as being present during the event. While matters of self-disclosure form a common challenge for much ethnographic research (e.g., Lohmeier 2009; Walford 2018), the question of whom we wanted to be transparent to, seemed particularly tricky: the organizers, the participants, everybody? After we reached out to the event organizers, it became clear (and was equally in the interest of the organizers) that we needed to rely on the same infrastructures as the event organizers if we wanted to ‘reach’ every participant. More specifically, the organizers asked us to provide a ‘catchy’ text for the newsletter, which was spread a couple of months before the event. Moreover, as already mentioned, the newsletter was equally used to invite participants for additional interviews. However, the organizers wanted us to not only research, but equally to actively contribute to the event program through participation in a panel on the main stage during the first day. Having agreed to this participation, one of our team members ‘merged’ into the event infrastructure at least partly differently than the rest of us did: not only was that member promoted in the program and app, s/he was equally displayed digitally, invited to the speakers’ lounge, and connected to other actor groups that came by for a talk afterwards. Thus, this active participation allowed us to become – at least partly – ‘normalized’ for the participants. Afterwards, many people knew how to place us, and many even showed interest for more information on the research project. In other words, having ‘digitally’ disclosed our presence to the organizers and participants before the event ultimately enabled us to observe the unfolding dynamics of the event from a more insider perspective, which would otherwise not have been possible. In contrast, by becoming an insider, we co-shaped the event significantly (see also Seim 2021).

Concluding remarks: the infrastructural co-unfolding of hybrid (edtech) events and hybrid (team) ethnography

The goal of this article was to contribute to expanding discussions on the rising ‘hybridity’ of (edtech) events and, in conjunction to that, of ethnographic (edtech) event research. While the emergence of the postdigital condition of today’s society and its methodological consequences for ethnographic research are increasingly discussed in the field, we argued in this paper that, within that discussion, few attention has thus far been put on how this hybridity manifests and is mediated through orchestrations of data infrastructures. Responding to that gap, our intention was to develop a more profound understanding of how the data infrastructuring of an edtech event on the one hand, and the data infrastructuring of ethnographic event research on the other hand, relate to, and impact, one another (see also Jordan 2009; Schulte-Römer and Gesing 2023).

As our findings show, this interrelation was far from deterministic. Rather, we found multiple dynamics unfolding *in-between* and *within* the infrastructuring of the event and the infrastructuring of the ethnography. To begin with, while during some stages of our research, both ‘backbones of infrastructure’ (needed to be) aligned (for instance, when we needed to make use of the event app to secure our interviews), in other stages we as a team deliberately created non-relationality (e.g., when using an own orchestration of digital communication spaces). In turn, *within* the infrastructuring of the ethnography, we continuously needed to balance out the ‘natural attempt for data integration’ and the safeguarding of authenticity regarding tools or practices – here in particular the analogue notebooks – that resist digital infrastructuring. Similarly, each platform or tool brought specific affordances into our research (and the event), which we carefully needed to navigate, complementing different affordance constellations with one another. In having discussed this all in detail, we also seek to offer a contribution to broader discussions around the significant *performative power* of ethnography, which not only refers to the ethnographic co-construction of the field one is investigating, but also to the performativity of the data infrastructures one is employing in the research (see also Lury 2021). It is through these infrastructures that particular kinds of

visibilities are being created from the field at particular points in time, for particular people, and in particular ways.

In sum, rather than providing a ‘how to’-guide to hybrid team ethnography, this paper aimed at showing the intricacies and manifold nature of doing hybrid ethnographic research in/as a team within the highly vibrant and dynamic setting of an edtech event. We hope that the detailed outline of how we navigated the hybrid unfolding of our research, and how, in the end, we orchestrated tools to best serve our needs while sustaining critical awareness of the performativity of both the event and our own actions, can serve as inspiration and groundwork for others in the design of their study, be it related to (edtech) events or other kinds of ethnographic studies. Based on the analysis above, in this section we briefly suggest some key guiding questions that can support a reflection-oriented orchestrating, and interacting with, data infrastructures in contexts of hybrid ethnography:

Creating and sustaining collectivity through/despite infrastructures

- Which collectives are relevant in your study (research-wise, field-wise)? How do you understand this collectiveness?
- Which ideas of collectivity are either inscribed in particular platforms or technologies and/or triggered through their setup/usage?
- How can it be secured that the gradual unfolding of collectivity – and the role of data infrastructures herein – can be observed and, if necessary, adjusted?

Data (not) becoming part of digital infrastructures

- Which data do you want to collect and how does hybridity play a role in this (e.g., where and when are the data that you want to capture)?
- Which forms of world-making are either inscribed in particular platforms or technologies and/or triggered through their setup/usage? Which options for adaptation are being offered?
- How do the need to infrastructure data/make data interoperable on the one hand, and the need to keep the authenticity of different forms of data collection and analysis on the other hand, play out in your study?
- How can it be secured that the hybrid unfolding of data collection and analysis – and the role of data infrastructures herein – can be observed and, if necessary, adjusted?

Researchers (not) becoming part of messy event infrastructures

- How can strategies of infrastructuring support you in preparing the ethnography and/or in reacting spontaneously to messiness or chaos?
- Which potential risks lie in the infrastructures of the event and how could they mess around with your research?
- How are you (as a team) positioning yourself to the event, and how are you (not) visible for the event through data infrastructures?
- In how far can infrastructures support your transparency towards the event? In how far does this transparency imply ‘merging’ with the infrastructural backbone of the event, and is this something that serves your research?
- How can it be secured that the own involvement in, and co-construction of, the event can be observed and, if necessary, adjusted?

For all these questions, we hope to have provided some initial inspiration and groundwork with this paper.

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Tracing the infrastructural unfolding of (edtech) events through hybrid team ethnography

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